

Increasing the Underwater Sensor Networks potential in Montenegro - an overview of the Horizon Europe MONUSEN project

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Abstract— This paper presents the ongoing Horizon Europe Twinning project Montenegrin Centre for Underwater Sensor Networks (MONUSEN) and provides an overview of the activities that have taken place during the first ten months of the project and future plans. MONUSEN strives to create collaborative conditions for the University of Montenegro to trace a clear excellence trajectory in the field of Underwater Sensor Networks (USNs). This will be achieved by twinning with European research-intensive institutions with strong expertise in this field: National Research Council of Italy, University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, and Newcastle University. The project has four main lines of action: scientific knowledge transfer, joint research on the design of efficient and secure USNs, research management capacity building, and broad networking with USN research stakeholders and industry. While all envisioned objectives of the project are listed, the paper primarily focuses on the research results and plans, and strategic measures for increasing scientific involvement and visibility.

Keywords— *marine systems, underwater sensor networks.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The MONUSEN is a Horizon Europe Twinning project funded by the European Union that was started in June 2022. Within MONUSEN twinning, Faculty of Electrical Engineering at University of Montenegro (UoM) aims to create a new research center dedicated to Underwater Sensor Networks (USNs). The basis for the realization of this plan is strong networking with National Research Council of Italy (CNR), University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (UNIZG-FER) and Newcastle University (UNEW) - the European leading partners which are globally recognizable

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by strong expertise in USN field, confirmed in numerous EU projects and other EU flagship initiatives, as well as by available research infrastructure, USN technology, and experience in field trials. The specific project objectives are:

1. To increase the scientific excellence and innovation capacity of UoM within three strategic research domains: USN communication protocols and security, USN data processing, and mobile USNs;
2. To create a framework for sustainable collaboration between UoM and the leading partners through joint research actions;
3. To significantly increase UoM scientific involvement, innovation potential, and broad visibility.
4. To strengthen the research management capacities of UoM;

The main strategic measures for achieving these objectives include know-how exchange, joint research actions, and organization of broad networking events. During the first ten months of the project, substantial progress has been made in implementing these measures. This paper provides an overview of the main results achieved, with a special emphasis on the joint research actions, which are focused on designing efficient and secure USNs for both fixed and dynamic topologies. To achieve state-of-the-art advancements, the project partners are working on the design and implementation of (i) machine learning-based adaptive communication protocols, (ii) lightweight decentralized authentication schemes, and (iii) cooperative control protocols for multi-vehicle USNs. In this paper, for each of these joint research actions, we explain the specific research

problems that are being addressed, the proposed solutions, and the research methodologies used. We also present the preliminary results and findings.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II we explain the MONUSEN strategic measures for research know-how exchange. Section III provides more details on the joint research actions of MONUSEN partners. Section IV provides an overview of MONUSEN's broad networking events that aim to provide broader visibility of the research results, promote technology transfer to industry, and foster interdisciplinary collaboration. Conclusions and indications of future work are given in Section V.

II. RESEARCH KNOW-HOW EXCHANGE

The strategic plan of UoM for stepping up and stimulating scientific excellence and innovation capacity in the USN field includes three main Strategic Research Domains (SRDs) on which MONUSEN will focus: (i) USN communication protocols and security; (ii) USN data processing; and (iii) mobile USNs. These SRDs include challenging USN research topics, in which the leading MONUSEN partners have great expertise. The overall approach towards reaching excellence in the above-define SRDs at UoM is based on the following measures for research know-how exchange:

- **Staff exchanges** - This activity includes UoM research staff visiting partner institutions. The goal of staff exchanges is to provide UoM visiting researchers with the opportunity to work closely with partner researchers at the host institution for an extended period and obtain first-hand experience with the equipment available in the host institution's laboratory.
- **Expert visits** - The exchange of know-how will be also supported by short-term visits of experts from the leading partner institutions to UoM. Expert visitors will provide a series of lectures with topics directly related to the defined SRDs. This will ensure the transfer of the highest quality theoretical knowledge in the USN field;
- **Trainings** - This activity includes one-week-long training sessions by a group from internationally leading partner institutions for all members of the project consortium. Trainings will include work with USN equipment and will provide hands-on experience and practical knowledge transfer.

So far, four trainings and one expert visit (Fig. 1) have been carried out. UNEW organized trainings on underwater acoustic communication, localization, and acoustic modem design. UNIZG-FER organized training on autonomous marine vehicles, sensors and applications, while CNR provided training on guidance and control of unmanned marine vehicles. In total, 6 staff exchanges, 12 expert visits, and 12 training are planned during the project lifespan. Similar activities will be conducted for research management capacity building.

III. JOINT RESEARCH ACTIONS

A framework for sustainable collaboration among the MONUSEN partners will be created through joint research actions focused on the design of efficient and secure USNs, for

Fig. 1. Expert visit of prof. Jeffrey Neasham (UNEW) to UoM.

fixed and dynamic topologies. In this section, we provide an overview of the main research results achieved thus far and describe our plans for future work.

A. Learning-based MAC protocols

One of the MONUSEN research objectives is to develop adaptive, learning-based MAC protocols for underwater acoustic sensor networks that can efficiently handle the dynamic and complex nature of the underwater acoustic channel. The learning-based MAC should offer an advantage over the existing solutions by enabling the (semi)optimal transmission strategy to be achieved and maintained in a dynamic environment with minimal communication overhead. One of the research outputs is a framed-ALOHA-based protocol that utilizes Q-learning [1] to select optimal time slots for packet transmissions, along with time offsets to delay packet transmissions within the chosen time slots. A star network topology is considered, where underwater sensor nodes periodically transmit data to a common sink node on the water surface. This topology is widely used in numerous practical UASN applications, such as long-lasting marine environment monitoring, seismic monitoring for oil extraction from underwater fields, and the Internet of Underwater Things. To address the MAC problem, we adopt a decentralized multi-agent Reinforcement Learning (RL) approach, treating sensor nodes as independent, asynchronous RL agents capable of learning optimal transmission strategies through trial-and-error interactions with the environment. In this approach, the actions taken by the nodes are evaluated based on the feedback received from the sink node. A node considers packet acknowledgments (ACK) as a reward indicator and ACK timeout expiration as a penalty. By observing these rewards and penalties, the nodes can learn and improve their decision-making process for better performance. Thereby, sensor nodes do not need to exchange control information with each other or rely on detailed network information such as link propagation delays. This reduces the communication overhead and simplifies the overall system design.

The idea of using RL to transform framed ALOHA into a solution that can adapt to a dynamic underwater network is not new. Our work is inspired by [2, 3], where the authors proposed UW-ALOHA-Q - an RL-based protocol for UASNs. Compared to ALOHA-Q [4], which is designed for terrestrial radio

networks, UW-ALOHA-Q incorporates three unique features that make it better suited for underwater environments. These features are: support for asynchronous node operation, a reduced number of slots per frame that entails improved channel utilization, and a random back-off scheme that helps the network to converge to optimal transmission strategy. However, UW-ALOHA-Q relies on a stop-and-wait transmission approach that requires time slots to accommodate data packet transmission, a maximum round-trip time, acknowledgment packet reception, and a guard interval. To optimize the number of slots per frame, a heuristic formula is employed that takes into account the number of network nodes and the network radius. Consequently, channel utilization depends on these parameters, and for certain network topologies, it can be quite low due to the use of large slot sizes and abundant idle time in the frame. Another UW-ALOHA-Q limitation that we address is that nodes adjust their frame start time through a random-backoff mechanism that fails to achieve network convergence to optimal strategy in a reasonable time. In order to overcome these limitations, we have implemented two main strategies. Firstly, we have decreased the time-slot sizes to enable more frequent transmissions by the nodes. Secondly, we have broadened the action space by allowing nodes to delay their packet transmission within the designated time slot. The first strategy, in turn, implies that nodes learn transmission strategies based on delayed rewards, i.e. the nodes can transmit regardless the reward/penalties for the previous actions have been observed or not. This, in general, negatively affects the learning process. However, as can be seen from Figs. 2 and 3, by jointly optimizing time-slot and transmission-offset selection, the proposed protocol manages to exploit the available bandwidth more efficiently than UW-ALOHA-Q.

Fig. 2. Training process of the proposed protocol and UW-ALOHA-Q (25 node UASN with 500 m radius)

Fig. 3. Channel utilization in the function of the radius of 25 node UASN.

B. UASN data security

Many UASNs applications involve a transfer of confidential data (e.g. natural resource information, military alerts). Thus, the second research track of the MONUSEN project is focused on establishing a secure communication channel between UASN devices. Compared to terrestrial wireless sensor networks, in UASNs security problems are more pronounced because the nodes are often left unattended for long periods, without physical protection, and the sensor nodes are usually more resource-constrained [5, 6]. Moreover, the underwater acoustic channel is characterized by a slow signal propagation speed ($\sim 1500\text{m/s}$), low bandwidth, and high attenuation, which leads to significant communication delays and increased energy consumption. The communication delays make it easier to carry out wormhole attacks [7]. On the other hand, the low bandwidth of the channel makes it challenging to secure the network effectively. In comparison to terrestrial WSNs, UASNs necessitate considerably more energy for data transmission, typically on the order of tens of watts [5]. Therefore, ensuring the same level of network security requires a substantially higher energy requirement. Given the aforementioned challenges, it is clear that the existing security solutions designed for terrestrial networks are not directly applicable to UASNs [6]. Addressing these issues requires innovative solutions that account for the unique characteristics of UASNs and effectively manage the network's limited resources while ensuring secure communication.

Initial MONUSEN activities in this research domain involved investigating lightweight authentication and key-exchange protocols that are suitable for UASNs. In [8], Elliptic Curve Qu-Vanstone (ECQV) [9] protocol is used for implicit certificate generation, and it has been combined with Hashed One-pass Menezes QuVanstone (HOMQV) key exchange protocol [10]. The study evaluated the performance of the ECQV and HOMQV protocols on several computing platforms with differing capabilities. The evaluation focused on the computational overhead and security robustness across different cryptographic parameter configurations. The findings demonstrate that the combination of ECQV and HOMQV protocols can offer a high level of security while minimizing energy consumption, transmission, and processing delay. In terms of communication overhead, the ECQV-HOMQV key exchange scheme is notably more efficient than the Diffie Hellman scheme that utilizes X.509 certificates (which are approximately 800B in length). Using 10B long sensor node identifiers as a basis for experimentation, the ECQV-HOMQV solution generated a maximum packet size of 30B and 42B for SECP160r1 and SECP256k1 elliptic curves, respectively. It has been observed that the ECQV-HOMQV procedure offers approximately a 10% improvement in timings when compared to Diffie Hellman with X.509 certificates.

Ongoing research activities are focused on providing efficient means of authentication in clustered UASNs with mobile sensor nodes. Fig. 4 depicts the considered UASN model which consists of a large number of sensor nodes distributed

underwater, over a larger area, and multiple gateway nodes on the water surface that facilitate the transfer of data from underwater nodes to the shore-side network infrastructure. In this particular scenario, the need for lightweight and fast authentication is particularly pronounced because nodes frequently switch between surface gateways due to intentional or intentional mobility. We assume that the security of the communication links is based on the ECQV-HOMQV procedure for authenticated key exchange. Further on, we assume that the surface gateways form a blockchain network to maintain network information and provide distributed certificate authority services for sensor nodes. The implementation of blockchain network is expected to eliminate the problem of single points of failure and protect against replay attacks by storing communication histories between the parties involved in the HOMQV protocol.

Fig. 4. Blockchain-assisted authentication in UASN.

C. Cooperative control of underwater vehicles

The third research objective of MONUSEN is to enhance cooperation efficiency in multi-vehicle USNs. As part of the research conducted thus far, a distributed control protocol has been devised to solve the output containment problem in USNs consisting of autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) and/or unmanned surface vehicles (USVs) organized in a leader-follower manner. In the considered cooperation scenario, the main task of the leader vehicles is to detect hazardous areas and generate the proper trajectories to steer away the followers to a safe region. The proposed protocol ensures that the outputs of the follower vehicles converge to the convex hull generated by the leader vehicles' trajectories (Fig. 4). In contrast to the protocols available in the literature, the proposed protocol does not require the impractical assumption that the controllers embedded in the followers have to share information [11].

In the early stage of the project, USV path-following problem has been also considered, with the ultimate aim of expanding the research to encompass the challenge of cooperative vehicle guidance. In a recent publication [12], an improved Line of Sight (LOS) guidance law for path following of underactuated USVs with sideslip compensation has been proposed. The LOS guidance principle is widely utilized for path following in marine vessels due to its effectiveness and simplicity. This

Fig. 4. Trajectories of the leaders and followers in a 2D plane. The leaders, denoted by squares, move in ellipses, thus forming a time-varying triangle. The followers converge to the triangle, thus achieving the output containment objective.

Fig. 5. Sideslip angle estimation in USV path following.

Fig. 6. Path following performance.

method generates a desired yaw angle that serves as a control input for the heading controller. However, using traditional LOS guidance is impractical in the presence of unknown drift forces that arise from disturbances like ocean currents, wind, and waves. The combined effects of these disturbances cause a deviation between the USV's moving orientation and its heading, which is known as a sideslip. Sideslip results in increased tracking errors, thereby adversely impacting overall performance [13]. The proposed approach estimates the sideslip angle as an unknown system state concurrently with the cross-track error utilizing an augmented extended Kalman filter (AEKF). This method differs from available predictor-based methods that use mutually independent adaptive gains to update the cross-track error and sideslip angle. As a result, the proposed LOS approach exhibits faster convergence speed and better path-following performance, which is validated through numerical simulations. Specifically, Fig. 5 shows that the

Fig. 7. Breaking the Surface workshop, Biograd na Moru, Croatia 2022.

Kalman-Filter-based LOS guidance (KFLOS) enables fast estimation of the sideslip angle, and the proposed estimator exhibits significantly faster convergence speed than the adaptive LOS (ALOS) [14] and state Predictor LOS (PLOS) [15] methods. As a consequence, the proposed algorithm has the best path following performances, as demonstrated in Fig. 6.

IV. BROAD NETWORKING EVENTS

The MONUSEN project places a significant emphasis on strengthening links with industry and end-users to enhance the scientific involvement and visibility of all partner institutions. This is particularly important for the University of Montenegro, which is the coordinating institution of this Twinning project.

EMRA [16] (EU-funded marine robotics and applications) workshop will be organized each year by one of the project leading partners and serve as a meeting place for researchers, marine research stakeholders, and industry. For researchers, the workshops will offer dissemination opportunities for existing work, and highlight new application areas for consideration in future work, as stakeholders and industry representatives will be stimulated to present challenges they face. For marine research stakeholders and industry, the workshops will offer novel approaches to solving marine challenges and a platform for directing future research. During the first year of the project, the EMRA event was organized in Southampton, United Kingdom. The event brought together 26 speakers from ongoing FP7/Horizon Europe projects, industry, marine robotics end-users, and stakeholders. The event attracted over 150 participants from six countries and diverse sectors, such as marine robotics, oceanography, offshore renewables, oil and gas, satellite communication, and the blue economy. This interdisciplinary event provided an excellent opportunity for networking and cross-fertilization of ideas related to underwater sensor networks, enabling technologies, and applications. The upcoming EMRA workshop has been scheduled for June 20-21 and will be held in Šibenik, Croatia, and will be organized by project partner UNIZG-FER [16].

To enhance the project's effectiveness in building connections with potential end-users and research actors in the areas of marine biology, marine archaeology, oceanography, and marine security (navies, coast guards, search and rescue units), three summer schools will be held during the project's lifespan. These summer schools will build upon the success of the Breaking The

Surface (BTS) summer schools [17, 18] that have been successfully organized by UNIZG-FER for the past 14 years, initially as part of the FP7-REGPOT CURE project and subsequently with support from the Office of Naval Research Global and other EU-funded projects. BTS 2022 (Fig. 7), organized by UoM and UNIZG-FER in Biograd, Croatia, was part of MONUSEN project activities. It gathered renowned professionals from around the world, fostering interaction and the sharing of knowledge and experience. In total, 198 people participated in the summer school. The programme consisted of:

- 15 lectures where the latest scientific research and results were presented;
- 6 field demonstrations that showcased the latest technology achievements made by research groups and companies;
- 8 tutorials which offered hands-on experience with complex and modern underwater systems;
- company presentations with insight from company professionals about their company and company products;
- an acoustic localization challenge - where the participants were tasked to locate a submerged pinger using passive acoustic receivers and a fast vessel, operating their localization methodology.

Overall, the summer schools aim to foster collaboration, promote knowledge exchange, and advance research and innovation in the field of marine-related disciplines. The success of the BTS summer schools highlights their effectiveness in achieving these goals, and the upcoming summer schools are expected to build on this success. In 2023 and 2024, UoM will organize the BTS summer schools in Montenegro with the support of all MONUSEN partners.

As an additional measure to catalyze new project proposals and collaborations, MONUSEN partners will organize two joint hackathons with the leading partners, focusing on specific issues related to the MONUSEN strategic research domains. The inputs from the EMRA workshops will help to link the hackathon topics to the industry needs. This will contribute to improved creativity and new innovative research ideas.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper gave a short overview of the most significant activities and achieved results during the first ten months of the MONUSEN project. Most of the activities were focused on

improving the scientific excellence of UoM in the USN field by implementing strategic measures such as staff exchanges, expert visits, and on-site trainings. The research and innovation impact of the partnership has been strengthened through joint research actions focused on the design of efficient and secure USNs, for fixed and dynamic topologies. Two wide networking, knowledge, and experience transfer events (EMRA workshop and BTS summer school) have been organized to increase scientific involvement, innovation potential and broad visibility of MONUSEN partners.

Future research work will continue in the direction of load-adaptive MAC protocol design, blockchain-assisted decentralized authentication schemes, and cooperative guidance control of unmanned surface vehicles. The experimental validation of developed communications solutions and control algorithms is planned for the second and third years of the project. Additionally, networking events will be organized to promote broader collaboration and dissemination of the research findings.

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DISCLAIMER

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